

Babi Na Uku A Matsayin Ginshiki Wajen Gudanar Da Bincike A Hausa

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Tsakure

Gudanar da bincike a Hausa, a yau, yana fuskantar barazanar annobar magudɓin neman ilimi. Wasu dalibai ba su son gudanar da bincike yadda ya kamata su yi shi. Wasu kuwa, suna dfuko aikin wasu, su gabatar da shi a matsayin aikinsu. A wannan bincike, an karfafa bayar da goyon baya na yin amfani da “Babi na Uku” a matsayin mafita da za ta sanya a kauce wa annobar magudɓin neman ilimi, a wajen gudanar da bincike na kundin digiri a Hausa. A cikin takardar, aka yi kofarin fayyace gudummuwar da Babi na Uku (mai taken Hanyoyin Gudanar da Bincike), yake bayarwa, a wajen saita binciken kundin digiri, ta yadda gudanar da shi zai kasance cikin sauƙi, ba tare da yin magudɓi ba. Haka kuma, an y bayani dalla-dalla na yadda aka gudanar da binciken Babi na Uku, tun daga farkonsa har karshensa. An gudanar da binciken bisa manufar bayar da haske ga dalibai da malaman Hausa, a kan muhimmancin yin amfani da Babi na Uku, a wajen rage annobar magudɓin gudanar da binciken kundin digirinsu. An bi hanyoyi biyu a wajen gudanar da wannan binciken. Da farko, an bi hanyar lura da ido na irin dambarwar da ke faruwa a tsakanin dalibai, masu gudanar da bincike da kuma malamansu da ke duba aiyyukansu. Na biyu, an bi hanyar karantawa daga wasu rubutattun bayanai, waɗanda suka yi bayanai a kan dabarun gudanar da bincike a wannan zamani. Sakamakon binciken ya nuna cewa, akasarin binciken da aka yi amfani da Babi na Uku, ya fi kasancewa bincike mai cikakken bayani na yadda aka gudanar da shi, ba tare da magudɓi a cikinsa ba, fiye da waɗanda ba a yi amfani da shi ba.

Gabatarawa

Bincike al'amari ne mai muhimmancin gaske, wanda idan ana gudanar da shi, za a rinka samun ci-gaba a cikin al'umma (Lemu, 2005:262). Kenan, rashin gudanar da shi kan kawo rashi ci-gaba ga al'umma (Tofa, 1995:9). Shi tsararen abu ne, wanda ba haka kawai ake yin sa yadda aka ga dama ba, dole sai an bi tsarin da aka keɓe masa, don a gudanar da shi (Kothari, 1990:21). Don haka, idan dai ana son cim ma manufar yin sa, to, sai dole an bi tsarin da aka shimfiɗa a wajen gudanar da shi. Wannan ne ma ya sanya wasu masana suka sanya “tsari” na gudanar da “bincike,” a cikin rukuni na dangin nazarace-nazarce na kimiyya (Bunza, 2017:13; Bello, 2010:3).

Idan aka ce abu na kimiyya ne, to, ana nufin abu ne wanda ake bin “tsararren tsari” don gudanar da shi (Longman (2003:592). Shi kuwa, “tsararren tsari,” wasu masana da manazarta na kallon sa a matsayin abin da ake yi don warware matsalolin rayuwar Dan'adam. Ana gudanar da tsararren bincike ta hanyar amfani da salon lura ta ido, da yin gwajin don tabbatar da abinda aka lura da shi, da yin amfani da wani ra'i domin yi ma “lurar tarke. A kimiyyance, maimaita gwada abinda aka lura da shi ɗin, domin tabbatar da bayananki gaskiya a kan abinda aka lura yake aukuwa (Horgan, 2006:314).

Annobar magudɓin ilimi, cuta ce ta neman samun takardar shedar ilimi, ta hanyoyin da ba a yi ilimin ba, yadda ya kamata (Ado,2021:154). Wasu daga cikin gurɓatattun hanyoyin da ba ilimi ya tsara a yi su ba, sun haɗa da yin satar amsar jarabawa. Akwai kuma, juyar aikin juna da dalibai kan yi, idan an ba su aikin a a su je gida su yi. Haka kuma, akwai rashin iya yin ingantaccen bincike. Kazalika, akwai magudɓin da dalibai kan yin a zuwa wata makaranta, su juyo aikin da wani ya yi, su kai shi wata makarantar, a matsayin kundin digirinsu . Daga karshe, akwai rashin

tsayawa su koyi abinda aka koya masu, wanda sharholiyar zamani ta dfauke masu hankala, wanda ko da ka koyar da su, ba su fahimtar abinda aka koya masu (Abdullahi, 2007:23; Abdulrahaman, 2009; Bunza, 2019:16).

Tsarin gudanar da bincike na fuskantar kalubale a nazarin Hausa a yau. Wannan yana da nasaba shigowar tsare-tsare na zamani, waƙanda wasu Hukumomi ko Mazhabobi na Turawa suka fito da su, irin su APA da MLA da Oxford da Harvard da makamantansu (Ado, 2020:104). Waƙannan Hukumomi (o Mazhabobi) suna sassauya tsare-tsarensu a cikin mabambantan shekaru, tare da sauyin zamani. Duk Hukumar (ko Mazhabar) da manazarta suka dfauka, sukan bi turbar ta ra'in da ta fitar a kan bincike. A nazarin Hausa, an samu turjiya daga "wasu" masana, na kin yarda da sauye-sauyen na sababbin tsare-tsaren da waƙannan Mazhabobi suka kawo na zamani a kn bincike. Wasu, tun tsarin APA na farko da na biyu, ba su sake salon gudanar da bincike ba, wanda Hukumar ta sassauya har zuwa mataki na bakwai ba. Wannan ya haifar da dambarwa a wajen waƙanda ke da akidar bin turbar Turawa da waƙanda suke son a tsaya a kan tsohon tsarin da Hausawa suka sani (Ado, 2020:63). A bisa hasashe na ilimi, ana ganin wannan shi ne ya bayar da dama ga dfaibai, suka samu lungunan da suka kutsa, domin haifar da maguƙe-maguƙen gudanar da bincike na ilimi a Hausa.

Babu shakka, duk wani malamin da yake koyar da dfaibai a wannan zamani, ya san da cewa, an shig wani zamani na "maguƙin ilimi." Abin nufi, an shiga zamanin da dfaibai ba su son gudanar da ingantaccen bincike a bisa haƙifanin yadda yake. Akasarinsu, sukan dfauko ayyukan wasu, su wanke, su tace, sannan su bayar ga malamai su duba masu. Daga karshe, sai a iske cewa, binciken da aka yi a wani wuri ko wata makaranta, shi ne aka sake dfauko shi, aka sake gudanar da shi, a wata makaranta ta daban. Don haka ne ake son a rinfa sanya babi na uku, domin yin taciya da tabbatar da cewa, babu maguƙi a cikin binciken

Shi Babi na Uku, shi ne babin da ake ba shi take ne "Hanyoyin Gudanar da Bincike" (Bello, 2010:33). Babi ne mai muhimmanci wanda yake zaman kansa a cikin rukunna babuka biyar ko fiye da ake gudanar da bincike na samun kundayen digiri (Ado, 2020:61). Shi ne cibiyar gudanar da bincike, wanda idan babu shi, za a samu giƙi a wajen gudanar da bincike. Haka kuma, binciken ba zai kasance na kimiyya ba, wanda ake bin turbarta, a wannan zamani. Wannan dalili ne ma ya sanya masana da manazarta irin su Murtala (2012:67), ya nuna cewa, bin salon bincike na kimiyya, shi ne kan taimaka a wajen warware duk wata matsala ta bincike (Ado, 2020:2). Kenan, idan aka sanya dfaibai suna sanya Babi na Uku cikin kundin bincike na digirinsu, to, za a samu sauƙin maguƙi a cikin bincikensa.

Matsalar da ta Haifar da Gudanar da Binciken.

An lura da cewa, maguƙin gudanar da bincike ta yi yawa a wannan zamani. To, amma, akasarin dfaiban da ba su sanya Babi na Uku ba, a cikin bincikensu na digiri, ba su iya bayar da cikakken bayani na yadda suka gudanar da bincikensu. Irin waƙannan ne suka fi yin maguƙi a wajen gudanar da bincikensa. Su kuwa waƙanda suka sanya shi, a cikin kundayen bincikensu, ba su samun wata wahala, a wajen bayyana yadda suka gudanar da bincikensu. Don haka ne ma, aka lura da cewa, akwai sauƙin maguƙi a cikin binciken irin waƙannan d suka sanya Babi na Uku.

Harkar maguƙi a cikin bincike matsala ce babba a nazarin Hausa, wadda take buƙatar a gudanar da bincike don gano ire-iren muhimmancin da ke akwai a wajen yin amfani da Babi na Uku.

Waiwaye Kan Ra'ayoyin Wasu Masana a Kan Babi na Uku

A zamanin dauri, a wajen gudanar da bincike na Hausa, ba ma kamar wanda ake gabatarwa a cikin Jami'o'inmu na arewacin Nijeriya, ana gudanar da shi a bisa tsarin babuka na yadda ya sawwaka, kamar yadda kowane fannin nazari na Kimiyyar Zahiri da na Halayyar Dan'adam suke yi (Ado, 2020:63). Da tafiya ta yi nisa, aka shiga dambawar rashin daidaito, a wajen "tsarin" yadda ya kamata a gudanar da shi. Wasu kan ce, a bi tsari gudanar da bincike a cikin babuka biyar, wanda ke furshe da sassa na "Gabatarwa" (a matsayin babi na farko) da na "Bitar Ayyukan da suka Gabata" (a matsayin babi na biyu) da na "Hanyoyi Gudanar da Bincike" (a matsayin babi na uku) da na "Taciyar Bincike" (a matsayin babi na huɗu) da kuma na "Kammalawa" (a matsayin babi na biyar). Wasu kuwa kan ce, kada a sanya sashen Hanyoyin Gudanar da Bincike a matsayin Babi na Uku, sai dai a haɗe shi a cikin Babi na Farko. Amma wasu kuwa, cewa suka yi, kada a sanya Hanyoyin Gudanar da Bincike, a cikin sassan na babukan bincike, da makamantansu da yawa.

A bisa hasashe, wannan kalubale na rashin daidaito a kan babi na uku, ya sanya lamarin gudanar da bincike ya rikice, a nazarin Hausa. Wannan dambarwa ta "tsarin" da ya kamata a bi, a wajen gudanar da bincike a Hausa, ta fito fili, a lokacin da wasu masana suka bayyan ra'ayoyinsa, cewa:

Da farko, akwai zancen da Farfesa Aliyu Muhammad Bunza ya yi, domin kawo sulhu a kan dambarwar gudanar da bincike a Hausa, wanda ya ce:

"Ashe ya kyautu Hausa ta fito da irin nata dabarun bincike
a gwada da na zamani domin ci gaban ilimi."

(Bunza, 2017:xx; Ado, 2020:3).

A bisa wannan jawabi, ana iya yin tambaya a kan cewa, wane bincike ne irin na zamani da za a gwama da na Hausa? Amsar ita ce, a riƙa ware Babi na Uku, a matsayin babi mai zaman kansa, maimakon haɗe kayan cikinsa a Babi na Farko ko kuma ƙin yin amfani da shi.

Ra'ayi na biyu, shi ne wanda Farfesa Ibrahim Malumfashi, ya fayyace wa manazarta cewa, duk abin da ake son ya samu cigaba, dole ne ya amshi sauye-sauyen zamani. Halin rikau, ba zai haifar da da mai ido ba ga nazarin Hausa, kamar yadda ya ce :

"A kullum ilimi abu ne mai faɗaɗa,
kuma yana ƙaruwa da kyautatuwa.
Binciken da aka yi jiya ba yana nufin
cewa shi ke nan an rufe kafar yin wani
mai kama da wannan ko kuma mabambancinsa ba."

(Malumfashi, 2009:4)

A nan, Farfesa yana nufin cewa, tsarin dauri da ake bi na gudanar da bincike ya sauya, domin kullum cigaba ake samu. Wannan kuwa, bisa hasashe, ya wanzu ne saboda sauyin da ake samu na zamani a wajen gudanar da bincike. Wannan ne ya sanaya ilimi ke faɗaɗa, yake ƙara ƙaruwa. Alal misali, a yau an ci gaba, ana amfani da Babi na Uku mai zaman kansa da ra'o'in bincike da bin tsari na Hukumomin Bincike da makamantansu.

Ta la'akari da zantukan waɗannan masana, idan dai ana son sha'anin gudanar da bincike a Hausa ya bi "tsarin" zamani, kuma a kauce a maguɗin gudanar da bincike, to, ya zama wajibi a karɓi yin amfani da "Babi na Uku," a wajen gudanar da bincike.

Manufofi Gudanar da Bincike.

Manufar gudanar da wannan bincike ita ce, a fayyace wa dalibai da sauran manazarta masu gudanar da bincike a Hausa, musamman a kan al'adun Hausawa, muhimmancin yin amfani da Babi na Uku, a matsayin Hanyoyin Gudanar da Bincike. Abin nufi, bayan gabatar da wannan takarda, ana sa ran dalibai da sauran manazarta za su fahimci cewa, Babi na Uku, a tsarin gudanar

da bincike, shi ne cibiyar da ke fayyace duk wani tsarin da aka bi a wajen gudanar da bincike, anda zai snya a kauce a magudfin gudanar da bincike..

Wata manufar kuma ita ce, ana son a dawo da martabar gudanar da bincike a Hausa, ta yadda abin zai dace da zamani. Kenan, ana nufin, bayan an gabatar da wannan takarda, dalibai za su fahimci cewa bin hanayar zamia, ta sanya Babi na Uku a cikin bincikensa, zai kawo sauƙin magudfin gudanar da bincike, wanda hakan zai kara kimanta nazarin Hausa a idon duniya.

Daga karshe, wata manufar ita ce, so ake dalibai su kauce wa annobar da ake fama a ita a wajen magudi na rubuta bincikensa, ba ma kamar a wajen rubuta Babi na Uku.

Hanyoyin Gudanar da Bincike

An bi wasu ingantattun hanyoyi guda biyu, a wajen gudanar da wannan bincike. Hanyoyin kuwa su ne:

Da farko, an bi hanyar lura da ido na yadda dalibai ke gudanar da bincike-bincikensu da gabatar da su a wajen jarabawoyin da ake masu, ta ciki da ta waje, domin kare kundiyen digirorinsu.

Hanya ta biyu, ita ce wadda aka karanta daga wasu rubutattun bayanai. Wannan hanya ce, wadda ta bayar da dama ga mai bincike, har ya iya fahintar inganci da sahihancin yin amfani da babi na uku a wajen gudanar da bincike.

Ra'in Bincike

Wannan bincike ne irin na “Zaburarwa” (Action Research). Shi bincike na zaburarwa, shi ne irin wanda ake gudanar da shi domin kara inganta wasu sabbabin fasasahohi ko wata madosa da za a bi domin magance wata matsala ko wani abu da ya damu mutane a zamanin yau (Nwankwo, 1984:67; Ado, 2020:36). Nau'in da aka zaba ya yi daidai da wannan bincike, wanda aka gudanar da shi don zaburar da dalibai da manazarta, a kan muhimmancin bin hanyar zamani ta amfani da babi na uku, a cikin kundayen bincikensa.

Ta la'akari da irin nau'in wannan bincike aka ga ya dace a dora binciken kan: “Ra'in Alfanun Sassa” (Structural Functionalism Theory) A cikin harshen Turance ana kiransa da sunan: “Structural Functionalism Theory” (Otite, 1981:21; El-Tabie, 2012:77; Mashi, 2015:29).

A bisa nazari, an fi danganta Charles Darwin (1809-1882) a matsayin Baturen da ya fara magana a kan wannan ra'i a fannin dabbobi masu rai, inda ya duba lamarin tsarin halittarsu da kuma amfanin kowane sashe da yake tsare a cikin dabbobi. Masanin ya yi wannan magana a shekara 1859, a lokaci da ya buga wani littafi mai suna: “Asalin Halittun Jinsina” (On the Origin of Species) (Otite, 1981:2; Langacker, 1973:15).

Daga baya, an samu wasu Turawa masana waƙanda suka goya wa Charles Darwin (1809-1882) bat a fannin tsarin zamantakewar mutane na cikin al'umma. Waƙannan Turawa, sun yarda da cewa, kowace al'umma tana da sassa daban-daban, kuma kowane sashe yana d rawar da ayke takawa a wajen taimakawa, a wajen ginuwar al'ummar. Wasu daga cikinsu, sun haɗa da: Emile Durkheim (1858-1917) da Herbert Spencer (1820-1903) da Max Weber (1864-1920) da makamantansu (Otite, 1981:2; Mahuta, 2000:61; Mashi, 2015:28).

A bisa tarke na nazari, an sake samun wasu masana masu rajin wannan ra'i, waƙanda suka kara faɗaɗa ra'in a kan turba ta madosar “Zumuntar Sassan Al'umma.” Wannan tarke shi ne haifar da wani ra'in da ake kira da sunan “Ra'in Zumuntar Sassan Al'umma,” wanda ta Turanci ake kiransu da sunan: “Concensus Theory of Society” da kuma “Intergration Theory of Society” (Mashi, 2015:29; Ado, 2019:48).

Abinda wannan ra'i yake magana a kai, shi ne, ita al'umma an ɗauke ta a matsayin dunkulaliyar abu, guda ɗaya. To, amma a cikinta, tan da rabe-rabe na sassa ko ɓangarori daban-daban, waƙanda suke jingine da juna, kuma kowane sashe yana da alfanunsa a cikin al'ummar da

suke (Bello, 2016:22; Ado, 2019:38). To, bisa madosar wannan ra'i, kowane sashe yana da muhimmancinsa, a cikin al'umma. Sassan sukan yi cudanya da juna, domin yin taimakekeniya ga juna, ta yadda, idan babu wani sashe, to, al'ummar ma da za ta iya wanzuwa ba a matsayin cikakkiyar al'umma ba. Kenan, kowane sashe yana da gudummuwar da yake bayarwa, domin cigaban wannan al'umma (Mashi, 2015:29). Alal misali, idan babu sashen tsaro, waƙanda za su bayar da gudummuwar tsaron ƙasa, to, ai al'ummar ba za ta iya samun sukunin zama ba, don kowa zai tarwatse. Haka ma, idan sashen lafiya, ba su bayar da lafiya ba, kamar yadda aka samu "Cutar Mashaƙo" ta "Korona," ai da kowa sai ya mutu, ya zamanto babu al'umma. To, amma da suka bayar da gudummuwarsu, sai aka samu waraka, ba ma kamar a ƙasashen Turwa, kuma al'umma ta ci gaba da wanzuwa.

Ta haujin wannan bincike, za a iya cewa, wannan ra'i ya dace da wannan bincike. Dalilin kuwa shi ne, shi wannan bincike yana magana ne a kan sassan binciken da ƙalibai suke gudanarwa na kundin digirinsu. Binciken yana nuni da cewa, kowane sashe yana da alfanunsa a wjen gudanar da bincike. A cikin sassan, akwai sashe na Dabarun Gudanar da Bincike, wanda idan babu shi, to, bincike zai samu rauni, domin ba zai bayar da cikakken bayani ba, na yadda aka gudanar da binciken.

A haujin ƙora binciken a kan ra'in, ana iya lura da cewa, ra'in da ka ƙora binciken da kuma shi knsa binciken, duk suna magana ne a kan abu ƙaya, watau alfanun sassa. Abin nufi, dukkansu suna magana a kan sassan abin da ake nazari da kuma alfanu ko muhimmancin kowane sashe na cikin abinda ake nazarin.

Tsarin Rubuta Babi na Uku a wajen Gudanar da Bincike

Babi na Uku, shi ne wanda yake da taken "Hanyoyin Gudanar da Bincike" (Research Methodology). Babi ne wanda yake ƙunshe da sassa guda uku, watau tsarin gudanar da bincike (Research Design) da mutane ko abubuwan da ake gudanar da bincike a kansu (Research Population) da kuma ra'in da aka ƙora a kan bincike (Research Theory). Ga bayanin yadda kowane yake, kamar haka:

Tsarin Gudanar da Bincike

Shi bincike, ba hakanan barkatai ake gudanar da shi ba. Ana gudanar da shi bisa tsari (Bello, 2010:4). Tsarin gudanar da shi yana buƙatar a tsaya tsaf, a mayar da hankali kan yadda ya kamata binciken ya kasance, na yadda za a gudanar da shi (Jumare,2017; Katsina,2021:47). Shi tsarin gudanar da bincike, kamar wani mizani wanda ke jagorantar mai bincike zuwa ga tsarin yadda zai gudanar da bincikensa, da yadda zai warware matsalar da yake bincike a kanta (Jumare, 2017:64; Akuezuilo1993:37). Don haka, ingantaccen bincike shi ne wanda aka tsara gudanar da shi. Kenan, ana nufin cewa, duk binciken da ƙalibi zai gudanar, ana son a ga tsarin da ya bi ko wanda zai bi a wajen gudanar da bincikensa, domin kauƙe wa mguƙin gudanar da bincike. A wannan ƙangari, an bayyana irin tsarin da mai bincike ya kamata ya tsara a Babi na Uku na binciken kundin digirinsa.

Nau'in Bincike

A darasi na "Hanyoyin Gudanar da Bincike," kusan kowane malami yana koyar da "na'o'i bincike" ko "ire-iren bincike" (Katsina, 2021:12). Wasu daga cikin nau'o'in da ake koya ma ƙalibai masu ƙudurin gudanar da bincike (domin samar da kundin digirinsu), sun haɗa da: bincike irin na bayani, da irin na tarihi, da irin na siffantawa, da irin na ƙalailaicewa (ƙwaƙƙwafi), da irin na halin da ake ciki, da irin na gwaji, da irin na dangantaka (nasaba), da irin na hauhawar ci-gaba,

da irin na zaburarwa da makamantansu (Nwankwo, 1984:39; Gandu, 2005:10; Bello, 2010:4; Ado, 2019:16; Ado, 2020:27).

Kowane dalibi ko wani mai gudanar da bincike yana da matsalarsa ta daban da yake gudanar da bincike a kanta (Akuezuilo1993:7). Don haka, manufar koyar da dalibai “nau’o’in bincike,” shi ne, ana son, su bayyana irin dangantakar da ake da ita a tsakanin matsalar bincikensu da nau’in bincikensu, a cikin kundin bincikensu na digirinsu. Sanin “nau’in bincike,” shi ne zai taimka a wajen sani da kuma gane madosar binciken da ake gudanarwa (Nwankwo, 1984:37). Kazalika, ta hanyar bayar da nau’in bincike ne ake gani irin ra’in da zai fi dacewa a dora binciken a kansa da kuma abarar da ya kamata ya bi a wajen gudanar da bincikensa (Ado, 2020:63).

To, amma, matsalar da aka lura da ita, ita ce, akasarin binciken da daliban Hausa suke gudanarwa, ba su bayyanan irin nau’in bincikensu. Wannan matsala ce babba, domin idan bai bayyana nau’in bincikensa, ba za a iya gane saitin inda bincikensa ya dosa ba. Amm, bayyana nau’in bincike a cikin kundin bincike, yanku rage matsalar magudin bincike. 4f

Mutanen da Za a Gudanar da Bincike a Kansu

Mai bincike yana gudanar da bincike ne a kan mutane ko dabbobi ko kwari ko tsuntsaye ko duwatsu ko sararin samaniya ko wani muhalli da makamantansu (Jumare, 2017:66). Kenan, duk binciken da ba a bayyana irin abinda za a gudanar da bincike a kansa ba, to, binciken nan yana da matsala, domin ba a iya gane a kan abinda aka gudanar da binciken da kuma wafanda suka bayar da bayanai a kan binciken ba. Wannan magudin gudanar da bincike ne idan ba a yi hakan ba.

A bisa nazari, ana bayyana mutanen da za a gudanar da bincike a kansu ta wafannan fannoni:

Ire-iren Wafanda Za a Gudanar da Bincike a Kansu

Wafanda za a gudanar da bincike a kansu na iya zama mutane ko ko dabbobi ko wasu abubuwa (Jumare, 2017:66). A nan, abubuwa biyu ne ake son a yi bayani. Da farko, ana son mai bincike ya bayyana ire-iren abubuwan da za a gudanar da bincike a kansu. Na biyu, ana son dalibi ya bayyana ire-iren wafanda za a nemi bayanai a kan ire-iren abubuwan da ake gudanar da bincike a kansu (Katsina, 2021:47). Alal misali, idan dalibi zai gudanar da bincikensa a kan fadar sarakuna, to, dole ne ya bayyana. Haka kuma, duk wafanda zai nemi bayani a kan abinda zai yi bincike a kansa, ya kasance wanda ke a dangantaka da fada ko wafanda suke da ilimi a kan fada. Don haka, babu yadda za a yi, mai bincike ya gudanar da bincike ba tare da fadin abubuwan da yake bincike a kansu ba, da kuma ire-iren mutanen da ya zai samu bayanai daga wurinsu ba. Yin hakan, zai kawo tabbaci da cewa babu magudin gudnr d bincike a cikin kundin bincike na digirin dalibai.

Yawan Mutanen da Za a Gudanar da Bincike a Kansu.

A binciken kundin digiri, kowane sashe yana da dangantaka da wani sashe. Alal misali, a babi na farko, mai bincike kan yi bayani, ya fadi ko yawan ko fadin farfajiyar da zai gudanar da bincikensa a kai. Farfajiyar da za a gudanar da bincike a kanta, tana iya zama mai fadi da yawa ko matsakaiciya ko ‘yar kadan (Akuezuilo, 1993:43; Juamre,2017:67). To, bayanin da ake son dalibi ya yi a nan, tana da alaƙa da fadin farfajiyar da mai bincike ya diba a Babi na Daya. A wannan bangare ana son mai gudanar da bincike ya fadi yawan mutanen da zai samu bayanai na abinda yake bincike daga wajensu. Wannan lamari dole ne, mai bincike ya shata yawan mutane ko dabbobi ko litattafai ko wasu abubuwan da zai gudanar da bincike a kansu (Nwankwo, 1984:100).

Lallai an san da cewa, ba duk wafanda (ko mutanen da) suke cikin farfajiyar da dalibi (ko mai bincike) ya yi niyyar gudanar bincike a cikinta, zai iya tatsar bayanai daga kowannensu ba (Akuezuilo, 1993:37). Don haka, ana buƙatar mai bincike ya fadi yawan wafanda ya zaɓa, don

gudunar da bincikensa (Nwankwo, 1984:100). Haka kuma, dole ne a fadfi dalili ko dalilan da ya za aka zaɓi wannan yawan mutanen. Idan kuwa, abinda za a gudunar da bincike a kansa ba mutum ba ne, dabbobi ne ko litattafai ko wani abu, sai a fadfi yawansu, tare da dalilin da ya sa aka zaɓi yawan nasu (Jumare, 2017:66; Ado, 2020:65). Idan aka yi wannan tsari, babu yadda za a yi dalibi ya yi maguɗin ɗauko bincikn wani, ya kawo wa malami a matsayin bincikensa. Kenan za a sami sauƙin maguɗin gudunar da bincike, idan aka bi wannan tsari.

Dabarun Zaɓin Yawan Mutanen da Za a Gudunar da Bincike a Kansu

Har ila yau, a wajen gudunar da bincike, akan so a san dabarar da mai gudunar da bincike ya bi a wajen zaɓin yawan mutane ko dabbobi ko wasu abubuwa irin su litattafan da zai ko yake gudnar da bincike a kansu (Nwankwo, 1984:100). Sai dai, abin sani shi ne, ba dukkan kowane mutum da ke cikin farfajiyar aikin mutum, za a iya tuntuba ba, akan binciken ba, sai daikawai a bi dabarar da za a iya wakiltar kowa (Bello, 2010:36). Don haka ne ake ɗaukar dabara ɗaya, a yi amfani da ita a wajen gudunar da bincike. Yin wannan tsari, shi ne zai ƙara wa bincike inganci da kima da rage mguɗin da ake fama da shi a wajen gudunar da bincike a Hausa. (Akezuilo, 1993:46; Jumare, 2017:68). Kazalika, ba yin zaɓin kawai ba, ana son ɗalibi ya fadfi dalili ko dalilan da suka sanya ya yi zaɓin dabarar da ya zaɓa.

Akwai dabaru da yawa, waɗanda mai bincike kan iya bi domin zaɓin yawan ire-iren mutane ko dabbobi ko wasu abubuwan da zai gudana da bincike a kansu. Wasu daga cikinsu sun haɗa da: “Zaɓin Kan-Mai-Uwa-da-Wabi” (wadda ake zaɓar waɗanda za a gudunar da bincike a kansu ta hanyar ɗauki-ɗai-ɗai) ko “Zaɓin Ganin-Dama” (wanda ake zaɓar mutanen da aka sani, don an san suna da abinda ake nema) ko “Zaɓin Son Rai” (wanda ake zaɓar duk abin da yake iyawa, domin ba shi da isassun kayan aiki) (Akezuilo, 1993:45; Nwankwo, 1984: 101; Ado, 2020:67). **Hanyoyin Tattara Bayanai**

A bisa tsari na gudunar da bincike, kowane nau'in bincike yana da fitattun dabarun da ake bi a tattara bayanai da za a tace a rubuta su a matsayin kundin bincike na digiri (Katsina, 2021:50; Nwankwo, 1984:37). Don haka, ya zama wajibi ga mai gudunar da bincike ya yi amfani da hanyoyi tattara bayanai a game da bincikensa, daidai da yadda nau'in bincikensa yake. Wasu daga cikin dabarun tattara bayanai sun haɗa da waɗanan.

Da farko. akwai bayanai da ake samowa daga rubutattun bayanai, waɗanda ake karantawa. Waɗannan sun haɗa da bugaggun littattafai da kundayen bincike da mujallu da takardu da jaridu da makamantansu (Bello, 2010:41). Dalibi (ko mai gudunar da bincike yakan samu bayanai da zai sanya a cikin kundin bincikensa ta hanyar karanta waɗannan rubutattun bayanai (Gandu, 2013:21).

Hanya ta biyu ita ce wadda ake samun bayanai aga hira (ko ganawa ko tattaunawa) ta baki da baki tsakanin mai bincike da waɗanda yake gudunar da bincike a kansu ko a kan wani Gandu, 2013:24). Duk zancen da ɗalibi ko mai gudunar da bincike ya samu a wajensu, shi ne zai tattara, ya tace, sannan ya saka a cikin kundin bincikensa na digirinsa. Ita wannan hanya, hanya ce mai inganci a wajen gudunar da bincike, domin mai bincike za samu damar tattaunawa da wanda yake gudunar da bincike a kansa, wanda hakan kan iya sanya ya gane gaskiyar Imarin (Bello, 2010:37; Akezuilo, 1993:54; Nwankwo,1984:142)

Saurare da kunne, ita ma wata dabare ce ta tattara bayanai na bincike. Hausawa na cewa “Ji ya kori gani.” Don haka, ta hanyar saurare da kunne na wata hirar mutane ko a cikin gidan rediyo da makamantansu, yana iya santa ɗalibi, mai gudunar da bincike, ya samu bayanin abubuwan da yake bincike a kansu.

Gani da ido ma wata hanya ce ta tattara bayanai. Hausawa na cewa, “Gani ya kori ji.” Wannan hanya ce da mai bincike zai tafi wurin da ake aiwatar da abinda yake bincike a kai, ya

gan shi, ya ga yadda yake da yadda ake gudanar da shi (Gandu, 2013:26). Ta hanyar gani a ido, mai bincike na iya tattara bayanai na amsoshin hasashen mai bincike. Ita hanyar lura, hanya ce ta kimiyya, wadda ake yin ta ga binciken da ke buƙatar ƙwaƙƙwafi a kan binciken wani abu da ke son a san shi a zahirance (Nwankwo, 1984:141). Abin nufi, mai bincike zai ga abinda yake bincike a kansa ƙuru-ƙuru da kansa (Akuezuiilo, 1884:59). A sanadiyyar son da mai bincike yake yi, na ya lura da abinda yake gudanar da bincike a kansa, yake sanya mai bincike ya “shiga-a-dama da shi” a cikin lamarin abinda yake bincike a kansa (Ado, 2020:70).

Wata hanyar da ake iya bi a tattara bayanai a game da bincike, ita ce ta tsara, tare da rubuta tambayoyin bincike, a ba mutanen da ake son gudanar da bincike a kansu, domin su amsa su (Gandu, 2013:24). Irin waƙannan tambayoyi, akan bayar da su ga mutanen da ake tsammanin sun san matsalar da ake bincike a kanta (Bello, 2010:37). Sai dai, wannan hanya ana yin ta ga mutane masu ilimin sanin rubutu da karatu (Bello, 2010:37; Akuezuiilo, 1993:49; Nwankwo, 1984:132).

Ra'in Bincike

Lamari na uku da ake anyawa a Babi na Uku shi ne ra'in da aka ɗora binciken a kai (Ado, 2020:75). To, amma wasu sun nuna cewa, lamarin ra'in da ake ɗora bincike yawo yake yi. Abin nufi, ana iya sanya shi a Babi na Farko ko a Babi na Biyu ko a na uku. To, a wannan bincike, an fi bayar da ƙarfin cewa, a sanya shi a Bbi na Uku, domin, domin Imurran da ke cikinsa ba su da yawa. Sanya shi a Babi na Uku, zai ɗan ƙara sanya Babin ya yi yawa. Shi nazarin ra'i, nazari ne na wasu hasashe-hasashe na ilimi, da wasu masana suke yi, a kan matsaloli na ƙalubalen da ke wanzuwa a cikin al'ummominmu na duniya. Wasu matsalolin sun haɗa da irin su sauye-sauyen lamurra, tsananin rayuwa da duk wasu matsalolin da suka danganci zamantakewar al'umma, wadda ta ƙunshi al'adunsu da harshensu da adabinsu da makamntansu.

A yau, lamarin ɗora bincike a kan bincike, abu ne wanda ya zama dole (Bello-Kano, 2012:103). Kazalika, abu ne wanda ya kawo ka ce-na ce, ga manazarta da masana Hausa. Kuma fa, a nazarin Hausa na dauri, akwai ire-iren waƙannan hasashe-hasashe na ilimi a kan asalin Hausawa da harshen Hausa da asalin Maguzawa da addinin Maguzanci (Salihu, ...) A bisa hasashe na marubuci, ana iya cewa amfani da ra'i na ɗaya daga cikin abinda zai kawo ragowar yin maguɗin bincike, a wannan zamani.

Dora bincike kan ra'i, abin nan ne da Hausawa ke cewa: “Shure-shure, ba ya hana mutuwa.” Abin nufi, abu ne wanda zamani ya kawo, wanda Hukumar Lura da Karatuttukan Jami'o'i ta kawo, ta ce a rinka koyar da shi da kuma yin amfani da shi a kowane irin bincike. To, Hausawa na cewa: “Zamani riga ne, idan ya zo, tilas kowa ya sanya.” Amma abin takaici, sai wasu manazarta Hausa ke neman guje karantar da shi a matsayin darasi da kuma ƙin yin amfani da shi a harkar bincike. Wannan nuna gazawa ce. Don an ce, a tashi tsaye, a koyi wata hanyar nazari ta kimiyya da yin amfani da ita, a harkar bincike, sai kawai a tayar da jijiyoyin wuya? Hausawa na cewa, gyara kayanka ba zai zama sauke mura ba.” Abin nufi, nazarin Hausa, nazari ne da ya kutsa cikin kowane irin darasi, don haka, kada a nuna gazawa ga duk wani abu sabo da ya fito.

Ya kamata a san da cewa, tuntuni wasu masana Hausa da al'adun Hausawa sun yi magana a kan ɗora bincike a kan ra'i da muhimmancinsa, kamar haka:

Da farko, akwai Farfesan Adabi da Al'adun Hausawa, watau Farfesa Sa'idu Muhammad Gusau, wanda shi ma ya yi bayani a kan ɗora bincike kan madosar ra'i, (a cikin Ado, 2019:iii) da ya ce:

“Nazarin Hausa ya cim ma wani zango a yau na bunƙasa ta fuskar shigarsa a kowane fage na ilimi a tunani da falsafa da kimiyya da fasaha da ire-ire da sauransu. Mun iso wani lokaci da idan za a yi rubutu na bincike na ilimi

sai an dora shi a kan wani mizani na auna madosarsa ko mahangarsa tare kuma da samar da wani ra'i ko tarke na mazhabar wani marubuci ko manazarci da ta kafu bisa turba ta mabiyansa.”

(Ado, 2019:iii)

Na biyu, akwai Dr. Yusufu Bala Usman, malamin tarihin Hausa da Hausawa da Kasar Hausa, wanda ya nuna cewa, idan ba a dora bincike kan wani ra'i ba, to, kamar ba a gudanar da bincike na ilimi ba. Ga abin da ya ce:

*Saboda haka, kada mu rinka kauce wa aikin kimiyyar daddale abubuwa bisa madosar ra'i, da bayyana humimman kalmomin bincike,.....
Babu wata nadama a gareni, na kasancewa mai bayar da madosar ra'i, domin idan babu ra'i, to, babu ilimi. Sai dai kawai a ce an yi magana a kana bin da ya zaburar da mutum.....(Fassarar marubuci)*

(Usman, 1997:4).

Na uku, an sake samun wani Farfesan Tarihi wanda ya fara jaddada lamarin dora bincike a kan ra'i, a lokacin da ya ce:

Masu gudanar da bincike-bincike a kan abubuwa mabambanta, sukan dora sakamakon bincikensu ko danganta kimar ayyukansu ko gudanar da hasashen ayyukkansu da tunaninsu da wani karan-gwaji (ko mizani). Idan ba haka suka yi ba, suna iya rasa madosar aikinsu. Idan kuwa tunani da gaskiyar abinda ake nazari a kansa, ba a hade suke a wuri guda ba, to, aikin duk da ake yi zai rasa ma'ana. Don haka, ra'o'i abu ne da ake bukata a wajen gudanar da ayyuka na tunani da neman ilimi.

(Yandaki, 2015:9) (Fassarar marubuci).

A bisa wadannan bayanai da manyan malaman Hausa suka yi, bai kamata a nuna gazawa a fili ba, na kin koyar da darasin ra'i da yin amfani da shi a wajen gudanar da bincike-bincike a nazarin Hausa ba.

To, shi dai wannan bangare, na amfani da ra'i a bincike, abu ne wanda yake da mata kai guda biyar da ake son dalibi ya kawo bayanansu, a matsayin dora bincike a kan madosar ra'i, kamar haka:

Da farko, ana son dalibi ya fadi sunan ra'in day a dora bincikensa a kai. A nan dole ne dalibi a lura da madosar aikinsa, ta lura da taken aikin, a ga inda aikin ya sanya gaba, sannan ya dauki ra'i wanda ya yi daidai da madosar aikinsa.

A nazarin Hausa na wannan zamani na karni na 21, an samu wasu masana da manazarta Hausa da Hausawa, wadanda suka yi kofari irin nasu, wajen samar da bugaggun littattafai da kundayen bincike, wadanda suka yi bayanai a kan wasu ire-iren ra'o'in bincike, wadanda dalibai kan iya karantawa, su samu ra'in day a dace da ire-iren ayyukansu. Alal misali, akwai:

1. Mukhtar, Isah (2010). *Introduction to Stylistic Theories, Practice and Criticism*. Revised Edition. Abuja: Countryside Publishers.
2. Gusau, Sa'idu Muhammad (2015). *Mazhabobin Ra'i da Tarke a Adabi da Al'adu na Hausa*. Kano: Century Research and Publishing Limited.

3. Shu'aibu, Mustapha (2013). "Tasirin Mazahabobin Adabi na Duniya a kan Tarken Adabin Hausa." Kundin Digiri na Uku (PhD). Sashen Koyar da Harsunan Nijeriya, Kano: Jami'ar Bayero.
4. Ado, Abdulrahaman (2019). *Ra'o'in Bincike kan Al'adun Hausawa*. Katsina: Government Printing Press.

(Ado, 2020:76)

Har ila yau, akwai ma Hausawa waƙanda suka yi rubutu kan ra'o'i daban-daban da akan yi nazarce-nazarc da su, a ilimi na halayyara ɗan Adam, kamar irin su:

1. Dr. Amina Lawal Mashi (2018), *Sociology at a Glance*. First Edition. Katsina:Lekan Press Ltd.
2. Auwalu Ado Aujara (2010), "A Brief Account of Philosophical Views on Language and Linguistics," *Jigawa Journal of Islamic and Legal Studies*. Vol. 2 No.2. Kano : Gidan Dabino Publishers.
3. Iro Sani da Mohammed Sada Bature (2014). "The Relevance of Socio-Cultural Theory in the ESL Classroom," *Taguwa: The Journal of Humanities*. Faculty of Humanities, , Katsina: Umaru Musa Yar'adua University.
4. Farfesa Munir Mamman (2012). "Bahausha Mai Ban Sha'awa," *Champion Of Hausa Cikin Hausa: A Festschrift in Honour of Dalhatu Muhammad*. Department of African Languages and Cultures, Zaria: Ahmadu Bello University Press.
5. Dr. Danmaigoro, Ahmad (2014). "Nazarin Ra'o'in Da Suka Shafi Al'adu da Dangantakarsu ga Al'adun Hausawa," *Himma Journal of Contemporary Hausa Studies*. Vol.5, No.1, Oct, 2014. Department of Nigerian Languages, Katsina: Umaru Musa Yar'adua University.
6. Asabe Kabir Usman (2008). "A Critical Analysis of Some Selected Theories of Folklore," *Taguwa Journal of Faculty of Humanities*. Faculty of Humanities, Katsina: Umaru Musa Yar'adua University.

(Ado, 2020:77)

Mataki na biyu, shi ne wanda ɗalibi zai kawo sunan wanda ya assasa ra'in da shekarar da aka haife shi. Abin sani shi ne, ana samar da ra'i a bisa wata matsala da ta wanzu, wadda ake laluben hanyar da za a warware ta. To, Allah, ta hanyar aiko da Annabawa, ya riga ya warware wa mutane, duk wasu kalubale na rayuwa. To, amma su Turawa, ba su amince da yawancin Annabawan da Allah ya aiko masu ba. Don haka, suna samun matsala a wajen warware kalubalolin rayuwarsu. Duk da haka, sai suka rinƙa yin amfani da tunani, na ilimi, domin samun hanyoyin warware matsalolinsu. Wannan shi ya haddasar da yin ra'o'i da amfani da su da kuma makarantu da mazhabobin da ke samar da ra'o'in (Dangambo, 2008:6; Shu'aibu, 2013; Gusau, 2015:5; Ado, 2019:21). To, a nan, ana son ɗalibi ya kawo sunan wani Baturen da ya fara fito da ra'in da ya yi zance a kan matsalar da yake rubutu a kanta, da kuma shekarun da ya yi rayuwarsa da kuma shekr da ya samar da ra'in.

Mataki na uku, shi wanda ake son ɗalibi ya yi bayani na irin matsalar da ta wanzu, har wannan Bature ya kawo wannan ra'i.

A sani cewa, sai wata matsala ta faru, ake gudanar da bincike a kanta. To, a wannan mataki, ana son ɗalibi ya faɗi matsalar da ta faru, har aka samar da ra'in (Ado, 2019:52; Akuezuilo;1993:21; Tikumah,2009:11).

Alal misali, kamar yadda aka samu bayanai daga rubuce-rubucen asu masanan da manazarta, waƙanda suka kawo wasu lamurran rayuwa, da suka haifar da matsaloli a zamanin

Turawa suna da yawa, ba ma kamar rikice-rikice da suka yi ta samu, a kaini na 16, a sanadiyyar zalunci na ayyukan leburanci, a zamanin fitowar kamfunna, waƙanda ake sarrafa abubuwa da injina, domin samar da abubuwan tafiyar da rayuwa (Cooper, 1990; Mashi, 2015; Ajaura, 2010).

A lokacin ne, akan tursasa wa talakawa, domin su yi aiki tukuru, su yi wahala, su yi wa masu hali aiki, a kamfanoninsu, a kan kuɗi kalilan. Su kuma masu halin, su samu riba mai yawa, suna jin daɗi. Bugu da ƙari, a wancan lokacin ne, akan yi amfani da addini, a yi ma talakawa wa'azi na son zuciya, domin su ƙara dagewa wajen yin ayyuka ga masu hannu-da-shuni. Zaluncin da ake nuna wa talakawa, a wancan lokace ya haifar da bore da yin zanga-zanga, da fandarewa Wasu talakawan, a wancan lokacin, saboda faɗin rai, suka yi ta kisan kai, da sauran ayyukan assa (Essa, 2012; Lemu, 2005, Nasr, 2006:108).

A irin haka, aka samu wasu masu ilimi, suka yi ta yin tunane-tunane, na hanyoyin da za a gyara zamantakewar al'umma. A haka, wasu masanan cikinsu, suka yi ta amfani da dabarun da Girkawa da Romawan dauri, waƙanda suka yi rayuwa tun a ƙarni na uku, don gyara zamantakewar al'ummarsu ta ƙarni goma sha shida zuwa sha bakwa i(Mashi, 2015:15; Cooper, 1990;Gaida, 2015; Tofa, 1995:10).

To, ana son ɗalibi ya yi bayani na ire-iren abubuwan da suka haddasar da ra'in da ya yi amfani da shi, a wajen ɗora bincikensa.

Mataki na huɗu, shi ne, wanda ɗalibi zai yi bayanin, madosar ra'in. Abin nufi, ana buƙatar ɗalibi ya bayyana abin da ra'in ke magana a kai. Alal misali, shin ra'in yana magana ne a kan tsarintaka ko sauye-sauye ko gudummuwar da aka bayar a kan wani abu? Shin, ko kuwa ra'in yana magana ne a kan wata halayyar mutane? Abin dai da ake so a nan, shi ne, ɗalibi ya yi magana a kan matsalar da ra'in yake magana a kanta.

Mataki na biyar, shi ne wanda mai bincike, watau ɗalibi, zai yi bayani na abinda bincikensa ke magana a kai, wadda take da kamanci da irin abinda ra'in da ya zaɓa yake magana a kai. Abin nufi, ana so ne, ɗalibi ya yi bayani na matsalar da yake bincike a kanta, wadda zai kwatanta da abinda ra'in da ya zaɓa yake magana a kai. Kwatancen abinda ra'i ke magana a kai, da wadda binciken ke magana a kai, dole su zamanto iri ɗaya da juna. To, an yi haka, an ɗora bincike a kan ra'i ke nan (Ado, 2019:77). **Sakamakon Bincike**

Sakamakon wannan bincike ya yi daidai da hasasHEN DA AKA YI CEWA, yin amfani da Babi na Uku a cikin tsari babukan da ake sanyawa a cikin kundin bincike na ɗalibai, na neman digirinsu. Binciken ya gano cewa, Babi na Uku, idan aka yi amfani a sgi a cikin tsarin sassa na gudanar da bincike, yana taka muhimmiyar rawa a wajen bayar da inganci ga bincike da kuma kawar da maguɗin gudanar da bincike a tsakanin ɗalibai masu rubutun kundin digirinsu.

Shawarwari

Bisa ga lamurran da aka tattauna a wannan takarda na neman mafita, a bisa matsalolin da ake samu, a wajen rubuta binciken da ɗalibai ke gudanarwa, an gay a kamata a bayar da shawarwari kamar haka;

Da farko, ta fannin ɗalibai, ya kamata ɗalibai su zama masu son ilimi. Bai kamata abin da yak da muhimmanci ga rayuwar al'umma, kamar ilimi, a ce ana yin maguɗin nemansa da samunsa. Dalibai su zamanto masu kishin nazarin Hausa, su zauna su koyi yadda ake gudanar da bincike a cikinsa, domin su riƙa gudanar da shi yadda yake.

A bangaren malamai masu koyar da dalibai da kuma duba kundayen bincikensa, su ma, ya kamata su rinƙa tsayawa suna duba dalibai yadda ya kamata. Duk dalibin da bai tsaya ya koyi yadda ake gudanar da bincike ba, to, bai kamata a amshi kundin bincikensa ba, a matsayin ingantaccen bincike. Malamai su yi wa Allah, su kare darajar ilimi, ta hanyar tsayawa a duba ayyukan dalibai, yadda ya kamata.

Daga farshe, ana shawartar gwamnati da sauran hukumomi da cibiyoyin da ke daukar daliban da suka kamala karatunsu, aiki, da cewa, su mayar sanya duba kundayen bincike a matsayin abinda ake dubawa kafin a dauki mutum aiki. Idan kundin digiri ingtacce ne, sai a dauki mutum aiki. Idan kuwa ba ingtacce ba ne, sai a ki daukarsa aiki.

Kammalawa

Wannan takarda ta funshi bincike da aka yi a kan rubuta Babi na Uku, na kundin kamala digirori. An shirya wannan takarda bisa manufar kauce wa matsalar da ake fama da ita ta annobar magudin gudanar da bincike a Hausa. A cikin binciken, bayan gabatarwa, an kuma bayyana matsalar da ta haifar da gudanar da bincike. Bayan nan, an kuma bayyana ra'ayoyin wasu msana da manazarta a kan rubutun Babi na Uku. Kazalika, binciken yana dauke da manufar gudanar da shi da hanyoyin da aka bi a wajen gudanar da shi. Abisa nau'i na binciken da madosarsa, an kao bayani na ra'in da aka dora binciken a kansa. Bayan nan, a cikin kwaryar binciken, an kawo bayanai na tsarin da ya kamata a bi, a wajen rubuta Babi na Uku, domin a kauce wa annobar magudin rubuta ingtaccen bincike a Hausa.

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